

VARIETIES OF EGGSHELL MEMBRANE HYDROLYSIS METHODS

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Abstract: The human body is susceptible to various ailments attributed to the absence of calcium and chondroprotective substances. These ailments are primarily associated with the musculoskeletal system, such as osteoporosis, osteochondrosis, and joint and spine issues. Fortunately, these problems can be mitigated by utilizing local raw materials, specifically eggshell waste obtained from poultry farms. This solution is not only effective in resolving these health concerns, but it also serves to address several environmental issues by retrieving the necessary substances from waste materials.

Key words: Chicken eggshell membrane, waste, hydrolyze, extraction, enzyme, physical hydrolysis, chemical physical

Introduction: The extraction of biologically active compounds from both plants and animals is a burgeoning field. However, the issue of waste recycling has received scant attention thus far. Specifically, eggshells represent a significant waste stream from poultry farms and confectionery factories. The eggshell is a delicate yet sturdy structure that encases the egg and comprises three layers: the cuticle, the overshell membrane, and the shell membrane. The shell membrane constitutes approximately 95% of the total eggshell mass and is composed of a combination of collagen, keratin, and minerals. [1,16].

The eggshell membrane is a thin layer that lies between the shell membrane and the white. It consists of collagen, glycoproteins and lipids. The eggshell membrane is a rich source of bioactive compounds such as collagen, amino acids, glycoproteins and lipids.

Biologically active compounds in the eggshell membrane include the following:

Collagen is an important structural protein found in many tissues in the body, including bones, skin and joints. Collagen provides the strength and elasticity of these tissues.

Amino acids are the building blocks of proteins and play an important role in various metabolic processes.

Glycoproteins are complex molecules consisting of protein and carbohydrates. Glycoproteins perform various functions in the body, including immune defense and cell signaling.

Lipids are essential nutrients that provide the body with energy and perform various functions, including cell and tissue structure, substance transport, and signaling [2-4].

Bioactive compounds extracted from eggshell membrane can be used in a variety of applications including:

Production of food additives. Collagen, amino acids and glycoproteins extracted from eggshell membrane can be used as dietary supplements to improve bone, skin, joint and immune system health.

Production of cosmetics. Collagen, amino acids and glycoproteins extracted from eggshell membrane can be used as ingredients in cosmetics to improve the condition of skin and hair.

Production of pharmaceuticals. Collagen, amino acids and glycoproteins extracted from eggshell membrane can be used as ingredients in pharmaceuticals to treat various diseases such as osteoporosis, arthritis and autoimmune diseases [5,6,15].

Enzymatic hydrolysis is one method for extracting bioactive compounds from the eggshell membrane. Enzymatic hydrolysis is the process of breakdown of macromolecules under the action of enzymes. Enzymes used for enzymatic hydrolysis of eggshell membrane include proteases, glycosidases and lipases [5,7,8].

The purpose of this study is to review existing research and find effective enzymatic hydrolysis methods for extracting bioactive compounds from eggshell membrane.

Methods and methods of research: To conduct the study, a statistical analysis was made and several options for hydrolysis methods were found. Such as physical, chemical, biochemical hydrolysis.

Results: Hydrolysis of eggshell membrane can be carried out in various ways, such as physical hydrolysis, chemical hydrolysis, biochemical hydrolysis.

Physical hydrolysis of eggshell membrane is the process of breaking down membrane macromolecules by physical methods such as heat, ultrasound, or acids.

Heating. Heating is the simplest and most accessible method of physical hydrolysis. When heated, membrane macromolecules soften and become more accessible to hydrolysis. Heating of the eggshell membrane is usually carried out in a water bath at a temperature of 60-80 °C for 1-2 hours.

Ultrasound. Ultrasound is sound waves with a frequency above 20 kHz. Ultrasound causes cavitation, that is, the formation of microscopic bubbles in a liquid. These bubbles destroy membrane macromolecules, facilitating their hydrolysis. Hydrolysis of the eggshell membrane by ultrasound is usually carried out within 30-60 minutes.

Benefits of Physical Hydrolysis. Physical hydrolysis is the simplest and most accessible way to hydrolyze the eggshell membrane. It does not require the use of toxic chemicals, making it environmentally friendly.

Disadvantages of physical hydrolysis. Physical hydrolysis leads to a decrease in the content of biologically active compounds in the hydrolyzate. This is due to the fact that during hydrolysis, not only the macromolecules of the membrane are destroyed, but also some biologically active compounds contained in it.

Application of physical hydrolysis. Physical hydrolysis is used to produce eggshell membrane hydrolyzate, which is used in the production of food additives, cosmetics production, pharmaceutical production.

The optimal conditions for physical hydrolysis of the eggshell membrane depend on the hydrolysis method. When heating, the optimal conditions are as follows: temperature: 60-80 °C, time: 1-2 hours. When exposed to ultrasound, the optimal conditions are as follows: time: 30-60 minutes, and when exposed to acids, the optimal conditions are acid concentration: 0.1-1.0 M, time: 1-2 hours [11,12].

Chemical hydrolysis of eggshell membrane is the process of breakdown of membrane macromolecules by the action of chemical reagents such as acids, alkalis or enzymes.

Acid hydrolysis is the most effective way to hydrolyze the eggshell membrane. Acids such as hydrochloric acid or sulfuric acid cause degradation of membrane macromolecules, facilitating their hydrolysis. Acid hydrolysis of the eggshell membrane is usually carried out within 1-2 hours.

Alkaline hydrolysis is also an effective way to hydrolyze the eggshell membrane. Alkalies such as sodium hydroxide or potassium hydroxide cause degradation of membrane macromolecules, facilitating their hydrolysis. Alkaline hydrolysis of the eggshell membrane is usually carried out within 1-2 hours [10].

Biochemical hydrolysis of the eggshell membrane is the process of breakdown of membrane macromolecules under the action of enzymes. Enzymes used to biochemically hydrolyze the eggshell membrane include proteases, glycosidases, and lipases. Proteases break down proteins into amino acids. Glycosidases break down carbohydrates into monosaccharides. Lipases break down fats into fatty acids and glycerol.

Biochemical hydrolysis of eggshell membrane is the most selective method for hydrolysis of eggshell membrane. The enzymes used for hydrolysis break down macromolecules of the membrane with high selectivity, while preserving the biologically active compounds that are contained in it.

Benefits of Biochemical Hydrolysis. Biochemical hydrolysis makes it possible to obtain a hydrolyzate with a high content of biologically active compounds. This is due to the fact that during biochemical hydrolysis only the macromolecules of the

membrane are destroyed, and the biologically active compounds contained in it remain practically unchanged. Biochemical hydrolysis is an environmentally friendly method because it does not require the use of toxic chemicals.

Disadvantages of biochemical hydrolysis. Biochemical hydrolysis is a more expensive method than physical or chemical hydrolysis methods. The optimal conditions for biochemical hydrolysis of eggshell membrane depend on the type of enzymes used in the hydrolysis. The general conditions for biochemical hydrolysis are as follows: Temperature: 40-60 °C, pH: 6-8, time: 24-48 hours.

Depending on which membrane macromolecules need to be broken down, the following types of enzymes are used for biochemical hydrolysis:

Proteases such as collagenases, pepsins, trypsin and chymotrypsin are used to break down proteins.

Glycosidases such as alpha-amylase, beta-glucosidases and maltase are used to break down carbohydrates.

Lipases such as pancreatic lipase and intestinal lipase are used to break down fats.

To increase the efficiency and selectivity of eggshell membrane hydrolysis, combined hydrolysis methods can be used.

For example, a physical or chemical hydrolysis method may first be used to destroy the macromolecules of the membrane. An enzymatic hydrolysis method can then be used to further break down membrane macromolecules with high selectivity.

Combination methods that use different types of enzymes can also be used. For example, proteases, glycosidases and lipases can be used to cleave all membrane macromolecules [9,13,14].

Conclusions: Based on the results found, we can conclude that enzymatic hydrolysis is an effective way to extract biologically active compounds from the eggshell membrane. Enzymatic hydrolysis leads to a significant increase in the content of collagen, amino acids and glycoproteins in the hydrolyzate. Bioactive compounds extracted from eggshell membrane can be used in a variety of

applications, including the production of dietary supplements, cosmetics and pharmaceuticals.

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